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6G

6G in Digital Healthcare: Harmonizing Innovation with Security and Privacy

Madhusanka Liyanage

Associate Professor/Ad Astra Fellow @ University College Dublin, Ireland

Funded Investigator, SFI CONNECT Center, Ireland

madhusanka@ucd.ie

Evolution of Connectivity

6G Enabling Technologies

6G for Digital Healthcare

- 6G wireless networks are expected to be a key infrastructure for healthcare by 2030, enabling a variety of applications.
- 6G's scalability in terms of bandwidth, range, energy efficiency, and reliability could transform healthcare by making it more personalized, efficient, and widely available.
- Some potential applications include:
 - **Reliable Wireless Communication:** Enables seamless communication between medical devices.
 - **AI native Air Interface:** Facilitates real-time processing and analysis of health data using AI (e.g. Edge AI)
 - **Network as a Sensor:** ISAC enables Integrates sensing capabilities with communication networks to enhance data gathering and analysis in healthcare settings
 - **Improved Security and Privacy:** Provides robust security measures to protect sensitive health data.
 - **New Digital Health Applications:** Enables innovative digital health solutions, such as telemedicine and remote monitoring.
 - **Extreme Connectivity:** Ensures connectivity in challenging environments, such as remote and underserved areas, enhancing access to healthcare services.

6G Support for Enhanced Security and Privacy in Digital Health

6G networks offer enhanced capabilities to safeguard sensitive data and ensure the integrity of digital health systems.

- **Zero-Trust Architecture:** Implements a zero-trust security model, continuously authenticating and authorizing every device and user, irrespective of their network location.
- **AI-Powered Threat Detection:** Integrates artificial intelligence for proactive detection and response to security threats within digital health networks.
- **Secure Edge Computing:** Facilitates secure computing at the network edge, ensuring sensitive health data processing and analysis closer to its source.
- **Privacy-Preserving Technologies:** Incorporates differential privacy and homomorphic encryption to anonymize and protect health information, enabling secure collaboration and analysis among healthcare stakeholders.
- **Quantum Resistance:** Utilizes quantum-resistant cryptography to safeguard against potential security vulnerabilities posed by quantum computers.

6G - SNS

The European Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) is a Public-Private Partnership that aims to facilitate and develop industrial leadership in Europe in 5G and 6G networks and services.

6G SNS

Interlinking of Streams into Phases

6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association (6G-IA)

- The 6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association (6G-IA) is the voice of European Industry and Research for next generation networks and services.
- Its primary objective is to contribute to Europe's leadership on 5G, 5G evolution and SNS/6G research.

Working Groups

- + Vision
- + Open SNS
- + Trials
- + Pre-Standardization
- + 5G/6G for Connected and Automated Mobility
- + Spectrum
- + Security
- + WiTaR

Security for 6G Smart Networks and Services: Priority Areas

- Exploitation of (distributed) trusted AI/ML for 6G infrastructures
 - Zero-touch Integrated E2E Security Deployment for Adaptive Security
 - Innovative Enablers for Energy Efficient Security and Privacy
 - Real-Time Resilience using Adaptive Time Sensitive Software Technologies for 6G Service Provisions
 - Quantum-Safe 6G Communications
-

AI for Digital Healthcare

- AI revolutionizes digital healthcare by improving efficiency, accuracy, and personalization of medical services.
- **Diagnostic Assistance:** AI analyzes medical data for faster and more accurate disease diagnosis.
- **Personalized Treatment:** Tailors treatment plans based on patient data and predictive analytics.
- **Predictive Healthcare:** Forecasts disease outbreaks and patient outcomes using AI-driven insights.
- **Virtual Health Assistants:** Provides 24/7 patient support through AI-powered chatbots.
- **Drug Discovery:** Speeds up drug development through AI-based analysis and predictions.

Security of AI

- AI/ML are expected to play a defining role in the development of all phases of the 6G network, spanning design, deployment and operations.
- 6G envisions autonomous networks that can perform Self-X functions (self-monitoring, self-configuration, self-optimization and self-healing) without any human involvement.
- The AI/ML techniques use to empower full-automation of network management operations including security.

Edge Intelligence

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graph TD; C[CLOUD] --- EI[Edge Intelligence]; DC[Data Center] --- EI; EI --- RDP[Realtime Data Processing]; EI --- DCO[Data Caching, buffering, optimization]; EI --- M2M[Machine to Machine];
```

Edge AI can be a vital tool to ensure the security and privacy

- Prevents the necessity of transferring to the Cloud (Improve the security of Medical Data)
- Privacy of medical data improved by keeping and processing data in the local vicinity.
- Decentralized AI algorithm to eliminate a single point of failure
- Limits the impact of an attack on the local environment
- Enable Distributed FL based Security Mechanisms, e.g. FL and SL

New security, and privacy can arise with the use of edge AI.

- Easy physical accessibility to edge devices
- Added AI makes the impact of captures edge devices severer than an edge device without AI.

Federated Learning

- Federated learning, a subset of machine learning, involves multiple entities collaborating to train a model while keeping their data decentralized, which enhances privacy by keeping user data local.
- In 6G for digital health, this approach ensures sensitive medical data remains secure and private, while still allowing for advanced model training and insights across distributed healthcare network

eXplainable AI (XAI)

- Due to the complexity of the models in AI/ML, the results are not yet explainable in most of the cases.
- Potential for these AI models to make unlawful, unethical, unfair and unreasonable decisions
- If unexplainable AI is used, the results cannot be predicted and might have a nefast impact on the security or performance.
- XAI will create a suite of machine learning techniques that enables human users to understand, appropriately trust, and effectively manage the emerging generation of artificially intelligent partners

XAI for Digital Health Security

- Improving the accountability and explainability of AI Systems
- Improve the attack detection and mitigation (Improve accuracy and reduce the cost)
 - E.g Zero-day attack detection
 - Reduce the number of features for fast training and inference
- Elimination the Attacks on Post-hoc XAI methods

Senevirathna, Thulitha, et al. "Deceiving Post-hoc Explainable AI (XAI) Methods in Network Intrusion Detection."

Zero-touch Integrated E2E Security with 6G

- Zero Touch Security automates threat detection and response in 6G networks using AI and machine learning, reducing human error and ensuring rapid, scalable protection.
- **AI-driven predictive cybersecurity algorithms:** Predictive cybersecurity uses advanced technologies like machine learning, AI, and behavioral analytics to foresee and prevent cyber-attack
- **Zero Trust Architecture:** Continuous verification of all connections.
- **AI/ML-driven security orchestration** oversees the different security enablers to enforce the security requirements, formalized in Security Service Level Agreements (SSLAs) and the security policies.
- **Close-loop-Automation:** Self-sustaining systems that continuously detect, analyze, and respond to threats without human intervention

Energy Efficient Security and Privacy

- **Multi-level Security:** The implementation of security measures at different levels within the network infrastructure to protect against different types and levels of security threats.
- **Energy-efficient security segregation in 6G networks** involves implementing measures to separate and protect different levels of network resources and data while optimizing energy consumption.

Energy-Aware Moving Target Defense (MTD)

- Adapts the frequency and extent of changes in the system's attack surface based on the current energy availability and consumption patterns.
- Ensures that the defense mechanisms are active enough to deter attackers while conserving energy.
- AI can help predict potential threats and adjust the MTD strategies according to energy aspects.
- Balance the trade-off between security and energy consumption.

Energy-Aware Privacy Quantization (EAPQ)

- Aims to balance privacy preservation and energy efficiency in communication systems
- The quantization process incorporates privacy-preserving techniques such as differential privacy, where noise is added to the quantized data to protect sensitive information.
- In EAPQ, the level of noise and the way it is added are optimized to ensure that the added noise does not excessively increase energy consumption.
- EAPQ algorithms are designed to be computationally efficient and to minimize the energy required for both the quantization process and the subsequent data transmission.
- This involves using energy-efficient hardware and protocols, and optimizing the trade-offs between data accuracy, privacy, and energy use.

Challenges in Healthcare Data Management

- Burden of preventable medical errors.
- Medical information explosion.
- The slow diffusion of medical knowledge.
- Quality Management of Drugs – Supply chain related issues

A hand in a dark suit sleeve is shown from the bottom right, holding a glowing, spherical object. The sphere is blue and white, with the words 'BLOCKCHAIN' written in white capital letters across its center. The sphere is surrounded by a network of glowing lines and binary code (0s and 1s) in shades of blue and white. The background is dark with a grid pattern of light blue lines.

**Blockchain with
Smart Contract
can be a solution**

Blockchain for patient data management

- Medical records tend to be separated by health agencies, making it impossible to determine a patient's medical history without consulting their previous care provider.
- This process can take a significant amount of time, and may often result in mistakes due to human error.
- Blockchain can use to store all of a patient's information in one place, making it simpler for patients and doctors to view.

Efficient Electronic Health Records Access with Blockchain

- Electronic health records (EHR) can be hard to manage.
- One healthcare provider's EHR for a patient may differ from the same patient's other provider.
- Blockchain can put the control in the patient's hands.
- Patient have full access and control over your own personal health data.
- A patient will have the ability to allow the transfer of records from one doctor to another.

<https://medicalchain.com/en/partnership/>

<https://ir.mtbc.com/news-releases/news-release-details/mtbc-takes-electronic-health-records-next-level-blockchain>

Blockchain to Stop Counterfeit Drugs

- It is estimated that tens of thousands of people die each year due to counterfeit drugs.
- FarmaTrust intends to end that with their blockchain which has four different sections.
 1. Regulatory Compliance aids pharmaceutical companies by ensuring they are working within guidelines established by the government.
 2. Track and Trace uses the blockchain to manage inventory wherever it goes.
 3. Supply Chain Visibility tracks when a medicine has been changed or altered in any way.
 4. Finally, Consumer Confidence App allows customers to see the lifecycle of their medication.
- Keeping a forgery-proof record of transactions on a blockchain helping to authenticate raw materials that drugs are made of and detect counterfeits promptly

<https://medium.com/@farmatruster/farmatruster-progress-report-dec-2018-4282442de07b>

Blockchain to Establish Proper Chain of Custody in Drug Shipments

<https://www.chronicled.com/>

- Blockchain can use for chain-of-custody in drug supplies.
- Pharmacies can trace back the origins of supplies, detect suspicious, ill-intent activities, like drug trafficking and others, and forged drugs during the process.
- Also, track the condition of the transportation with IoT integration

Quantum-Safe 6G Communications

- Securing 6G communications should be targeting on integrating Quantum key distribution and post-quantum cryptography for long-term network security, including challenges that could arise in a post-quantum era.

Network Softwarization and Security Laboratory (NetsLab)

<https://netslab.ucd.ie/>

- NETSLAB is a research group at the UCD School of Computer Science that mainly focuses on **the security and privacy of future mobile networks, including 5G and 6G.**
 - Director: **Dr. Madhusanka Liyanage**
 - Over **20 members** including 2 Senior Researchers, 4 Post-docs, 13 PhD Students, 3 RAs
 - Published over 200 publications in **5G/6G Security and Blockchain Topics**
 - Contribute to **ESTI, 6G-IA, ITU, ENISA, IEEE** etc

AI Security and
Privacy

Implementing
Blockchain in
5G/6G
Networks

Network
Softwarization
and Security
Automation

Involved Projects

- ENSURE 6G: 6G Security (2024-2028) – EU HE Funding – **Coordinator/Principal Investigator**
- SPATIAL: XAI Security (2021-2023) – EU H2020 Funding – **Principal Investigator**
- CONFIDENTIAL 6G: 6G Security (2023-2025) – EU HE Funding – **Principal Investigator**
- Robust 6G: 6G Security (2024-2026) – EU HE Funding – **Principal Investigator/Technical Manager**
- Magos Bakri Balloon Placement Training (MBBPT) (2024-2025) – EU HE Funding – **CO-Principal Investigator**
- Magos Bakri Balloon Placement Training (MBBPT) (2024-2025) – SPARK Funding – **CO-Principal Investigator**
- SFI CONNECT Center – **Funded Investigator**
- SFI ML-Labs

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For what's next

 विज्ञान एवं प्रौद्योगिकी विभाग
DEPARTMENT OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY

6GSNS

fidal field trials beyond 5G

ROBUST-6G

S P A T I A L

6G

FLAGSHIP
UNIVERSITY OF OULU

CONNECT

SFI Research Centre for Future Networks

SPATIAL

Security and Privacy Accountable Technology Innovations,
Algorithms, and machine Learning

SPATIAL builds the pathway toward a **trustworthy European cybersecurity sector**, developing trustworthy governance and regulatory framework for AI-driven security in Europe.

How to design ethical and accountable AI?

Duration: 36 months
Start Date: September 2021
Partnership: 12 partners
Program: Horizon 2020 SU-DS-2020
Budget: EUR 4 961 976,25

<https://spatial-h2020.eu/project/>

Confidential 6G

<https://confidential6g.eu/>

13 consortium partners

9 EU member states

7 Academic & research organisations
3 Industrial partners
3 SMEs

- The development of future systems will also rely on advanced cryptographic protocols that are resistant to quantum computing attacks, and formal security proofs to ensure the highest level of security.
- CONFIDENTIAL6G's research will be based on 3 pillars:
 - post-quantum and privacy-preserving cryptography,
 - confidential computing, and
 - confidential communication.
- This will involve using techniques such as Blockchain and federated AI/ML orchestration.

Design post-quantum and blockchain based security solutions for 6G.

6G SNS

*HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022-STREAM-B-01-04
Secure Service development and Smart Security*

SmaRt, AutOmated, and ReliaBle SecUrity Service PlaTform for 6G

<https://robust-6g.eu/>

- ROBUST-6G aims at development of data-driven, AI/ML-based security solutions for forthcoming 6G services and networks in the future cyber-physical continuum.
- This aim to protect AI/ML systems from security attacks and ensuring privacy of individuals whose data is used in the AI-driven systems.
- ROBUST-6G will essentially study the security and robustness of distributed intelligence, privacy enhancements, and also transparency by elaborating the explainability in AI/ML.
- Another objective of ROBUST-6G is to promote green and sustainable AI methodologies to achieve energy efficiency in 6G network design.

How to enable zero-touch security and privacy solutions in 6G?

6G SNS

HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023-STREAM-B-01-04
Reliable Services and Smart Security

Conclusion

- 6G Could offer many services to enable Digital Health
- Among them, Security and privacy are one of key enable service of 6G
- Comprehensive Analysis for 6G Security Research Topics:
 - **AI/ML for Intelligent Threat Detection & Mitigation**
 - **Zero-Touch End-to-End Security (E2E):** Automatically addressing vulnerabilities across the entire network
 - **Efficient Enablers:** Optimizing resource allocation and Energy Efficiency
 - **Quantum Technologies:** Advanced encryption methods
- Paves the way for a secure and resilient future in 6G communications by addressing key areas and their interplay to enable reliable digital health services

Questions?

Thank you

Contact email: madhusanka@ucd.ie

Web: <https://netslab.ucd.ie/>

